

Publish Educational Materials as Open Educational Resources

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- Only use your own or openly licensed third-party materials.
Info: Citing materials will be done according to current academic practice.
- 🔍 I search for openly licensed materials on search portals.
- 🔍 Correct labelling of third-party materials in general according to the [TASLL rule](#): Title, Author, Source, Licence, Link to the licence.

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- 🔍 Our [Licence Chooser](#) can support you choosing the best license.

- **Swiss OER Repository:** [Switch OER](#) (For all kinds of materials, curated by the ZHAW library team)
- **Video:** [Kaltura Mediaspace](#) (ZHAW video platform), [Vimeo](#), [YouTube](#) (with reservations: limited download function)
- **Images:** [Wikimedia](#), [Flickr](#), [Pixabay](#)
- **Other:** [GitHub](#), [Zenodo](#), [ZHAW digitalcollection](#)
Info: Example of file formats for processing: PDF, JPG, PNG, SVG, MP3, MP4.

ZHAW

Documents and tools
[Leaflet on CC licences](#)
[Consent form](#) (Word doc)
[OER policy of ZHAW](#)

Training
[FAQ to OER \(Moodle\)](#)
[OER courses & workshops](#)

Contact the OER team
 Enquiries: oer.hsb@zhaw.ch
[OER website of ZHAW](#)

INFOS & LINKS

Creative Commons in a nutshell
[What are CC licences?](#)
[Licence Chooser](#)
[Compatibility of CC licences](#)
[TASLL rule explained](#)

OER search engines (examples) Collection: [Finding OER Creative Commons](#)
Search indexes: [OERSI](#), [Switch OER](#)
Icons: [Noun Project](#)

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Photo: [Example on Wikimedia](#)
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